

Dry matter change (%)

Dry matter change of 188 rice cultivars under enhanced UV-B radiation in the glasshouse compared with the UV-B level of their origin.

Rice cultivars used in this study showed a range of morphological changes and dry matter production to enhanced UV-B irradiation, although response varied among cultivars and groups (Table 1). About 28 of the test materials significantly reduced their leaf area, 32% significantly reduced their plant dry weight, and 76% significantly reduced their plant height. Indica and japonica groups did not differ much in plant height reduction. More reduction in tiller number (22%), leaf area (33%), and plant dry weight (34%), however, were observed in indicas than in japonicas under the UV-B treatment. Although the number of cultivars tested was small, the javanica rices now classified as tropical japonicas are more sensitive than temperate japonicas.

Because the ambient UV-B radiation level at lower latitudes is greater than that at higher latitudes, it is generally assumed that rice cultivars originating near the equator are more tolerant of UV-B radiation. The results of this study indicate that this hypothesis is not true.

The correlation ($r^2=0.01$) between dry matter changes under enhanced UV-B and ambient UV-B level at the site of origin was not significant (see figure). Even after removing the nine hybrid rice cultivars from the plot, the r^2 value was still nonsignificant.

Six rice cultivars with significantly increased biomass production under elevated UV-B did, however, originate from high UV-B areas (7-8 kJ/m² per d). DNJ164, DNJ46, and DNJ85 (aus rice) are grown in Bangladesh during summer, when UV-B levels are highest. Yunlen 19, Guze, and Musang A are indigenous to high elevation areas where prevailing UV-B irradiance is most likely high (see figure). The UV-B-tolerant cultivars evaluated in this study might be used as possible donors in a breeding program, but the genetic bases and makeup for their response differences must be further examined. ■

Stress tolerance—drought

Changes in water content of rice grain during water deficit

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Water content of cereal grains decreases during maturity. Environmental stresses such as extreme temperature or water deficit, however, may cause abrupt changes in grain water content and result in seed shriveling and discoloration, delayed ripening, and poor grain quality. Similarly, rapid reduction in water content of grains can result in poor seed germination and seed deterioration.

Five rice cultivars (AUS257, AUS196, UPLRi-7, IR43, and IRAT104) were seeded on several dates during the dry season under upland conditions with sprinkler irrigation. Plots were at different growth stages when a 12-d water deficit was imposed. Maximum water deficit was observed at the end of

the 12-d water deficit when ψ_{panicle} was -0.8 MPa.

Panicle water potential was measured at dawn (0400-0600 h) using a pressure chamber. Developing grains were collected at 2- to 3-d intervals starting at 4-7 d after panicle emergence, and their water content and dry weights were determined gravimetrically. Rates of change were determined on the linear portion of dry weight and water content by least square method.

Grain dry weight, which generally followed a sigmoidal pattern, increased after panicle emergence regardless of water deficit; only slight differences in rates, however, were observed among most of the cultivars. During the panicle

Changes in grain dry weight (a) and water content (b) during water deficit.

Changes in grain dry weight and water content of rice stressed at different stages after panicle emergence.^a

PE ^b before maximum WD ^c (d)	Cultivar	Change in dry weight		Change in water content		Water loss and dry weight relationship	
		(mg/d)	r	(%/d)	r	slope	r
20-25	AUS257	1.8	0.97**	3.8	0.98**	-0.33	0.97**
15-19	AUS196	1.4	0.98**	5.5	0.99**	-0.27	0.92**
15-19	UPLRI-7	1.7	0.96**	2.5	0.99**	-0.43	0.95**
10-14	AUS257	0.8	0.88*	3.3	0.99**	-0.41	0.98**
10-14	IRAT104	2.4	0.98**	4.2	0.91**	-0.82	0.92**
5-9	IR43	1.1	0.98**	2.4	0.99**	-0.42	0.96**
0-4	UPLRI-7	1.7	0.99**	1.9	0.98**	-0.68	0.99**
0-4	UPLRI-7	1.7	0.98**	1.8	0.99**	-0.80	0.96**
SD		0.45		1.2		0.20	

*, ** = significant and highly significant, respectively, at the 5% level. ^aPE = panicle emergence. ^bWD = water deficit.

emergence period of 10-14 d before maximum water deficit, AUS257, a small-seeded cultivar, increased grain dry weight by 0.8 mg/d while IRAT104, a large-seeded cultivar, increased its

grain dry weight by 2.4 mg/d (see table).

Except for AUS257, water content was almost constant until 5-6 d after panicle emergence, after which it decreased almost linearly. At harvest,

grain water content ranged from 10 to 30% (see figure). Rice grain lost less water when panicle emergence was close to maximum water deficit (UPLRI-7 grain lost 1.8% water/d) than when panicles emerged between 15 and 19 d before maximum water deficit (grain lost 2.5% water/d). IRAT104 lost 4.2% water/d compared with AUS257, which lost only 3.3% water/d, even though their panicles emerged within the same period.

Grain water content and grain dry weight were negatively correlated (see table). The leveling off in dry weight was not accompanied by leveling off in water content because water loss continued for a few more days. These findings suggest that even if grain is fully mature, it continues to lose water even under water deficit. Results also suggest that a decrease in water loss in the grain was due to low water status during water deficit and not mainly to maturation. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Kairala (Ptb49), a high-yielding rice variety with multiple resistance from Kerala, India

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Popular high-yielding rice varieties of Kerala—Jyothi, Pavizham, and Annapoorna—were crossed with highly adaptable IR36 in a breeding program to develop varieties with multiple resistance to pests. Single plants with desired attributes were selected from the segregating population.

KAU8754, a promising culture isolated from the cross IR36/Jyothi, showed high yield potential and moderate to high levels of resistance to leaf blast, neck blast, sheath blight, gall midge biotypes 1 and 4, and whitebacked planthopper. This elite line was released as Kairali (Ptb49) in 1993.

The variety was highly promising in station trials from 1987 to 1991, with a mean yield of 4.1 t/ha. In the 1991-92 kharif (dry) season, the variety yielded a

mean of 5.2 t/ha across 23 locations in the All India Coordinated Trials, indicating high adaptability to different soil and environmental conditions (see table). The mean yield of Kairali was 500 kg/ha higher than Ratna, the check variety.

Grain is long bold with red kernels. Milling and cooking qualities are excellent.

Performance of Kairali at different sites in India.

Location	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	
	Kairali	Ratna
Kerala	4.7	4.1
Tamil Nadu	5.4	5.5
Karnataka	4.7	4.1
Andhra Pradesh	4.6	4.0
Maharashtra	3.2	2.8
Haryana	6.8	6.3
Rajasthan	5.4	5.4
Punjab	5.0	4.3
Jammu and Kashmir	5.5	4.0
Mean ^a	5.2	4.7

^aMean of two seasons at 23 locations.

With a duration of 110-115 d, the variety is recommended for all three rice-growing seasons of Kerala (kharif, rabi [wet], and summer). ■

Zhefu No. 9, a new indica rice variety in central and eastern China

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Zhefu No.9, derived from cross 44-1086/IR50, was released in Apr 1993 for use as an early season (April to July) indica variety in the double-cropped area of central and eastern China.

Zhefu No. 9 is a short-duration, semidwarf indica rice. It is 80-85 cm tall and has 105-110 d growth duration. Average yield is about 6.6 t/ha under normal cultivation and maximum yield is 8.8 t/ha under high fertilization and good management, which was 8.1-18.7% and 4.3-20.1% more than the checks,